

Remote-control of multi appliances based latching circuit and DTMF

Jabbar Shatti Jahlool

Department of Computer Technique's Engineering, Dijlah University College, Baghdad, Iraq

Article Info

Article history:

Received Aug 31, 2020

Revised Nov 21, 2021

Accepted Dec 30, 2021

Keywords:

Digital comparator

DTMF

GSM

Home appliances'

Remote control

Wireless

ABSTRACT

There are multiple technologies used to remotely control electric appliances like Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, global system for mobile (GSM), and dual-tone multi-frequency (DTMF), but these technologies contain limitations, whether by coverage distance or by the number of devices that are controlled remotely. In this paper, these restrictions were overcome with the use of DTMF and digital latching devices, which doubles the number of remote-controlled electrical appliances compared to other research using the same intended technology DTMF. Using the proposed mechanism in this paper enables the users to effectively control several electric remote devices equal to the standard number of mobile keypad buttons, so in this way, can control 12 devices. This is via the mobile phone by sending commands in the form of analog tones through calling to auto-answer remote control panel phone (RCPP). An interesting feature of this research, each keypad key of the owner mobile (OM) using to control one remote electric device to switch it ON or OFF, so that the first pressing will cause to switch it ON and the second pressing caused to switching it OFF. This method is used instead of using two keypad keys, one for ON and the other for OFF. The proposed idea working is the same as manually switching but here remotely and electronically. This feature is achieved by using a D-latch digital circuit. The work is implemented and tested by using Proteus simulation program.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Jabbar Shatti Jahlool

Department of Computer Technique's Engineering, Dijlah University College

Baghdad, Iraq

Email: jabbar.shatti@duc.edu.iq

1. INTRODUCTION

Controlling home appliances remotely is one of the important applications required today. To achieve this, the first thing that a researcher or thinker thinks about is taking advantage of the technologies that exist in the country and one of these is the mobile networks whose existence has become part of the lives of the people that cannot be dispensed with, in addition to the presence of their infrastructure and its coverage everywhere. Using mobile phones to turn on/off appliances is one of the effective solutions used for different places such as homes, offices, institutions, factories, banks, and others, especially in large sites that contain few operators compared to a large number of devices, or in other words to reduce the number of operators in large sites.

Using android mobile and microcontrollers with wireless techniques as remote control tools for home appliances control, but this system has a working limitation in the range of response that is limited from 10 to 100 m, this is because using 2.4 GHz Bluetooth technique [1]. A modern method for controlling home appliances, using the smart home system, based on the Internet of things and four types of sensors,

namely temperature, PIR, ultrasonic, and smoke gas sensors for intrusion detection and automatic environmental control [2], [3].

Design and implementation of home automation system based on DTMF, the system allow the user to control 5 different electric appliances anywhere and anytime [4]. Implement effective automation-based DTMF technology to overcome the drawback of using Bluetooth and Wi-Fi which are limited in range restrictions. Two keypad phone numbers are used to control one device, and as a result, this model also contains limiters, which are control a small number of electrical devices, i.e. as much as half the number of the phone's keypad numbers [5].

Depending on the availability of mobile services, including the use of the technique of pressing the mobile phone key during a call for the purpose of generating DTMF tone signals, and using these signals for the purposes of controlling home appliances from remote places [6]–[8]. Live video and audio monitor tools by using smartphones and internet service for the child or aged person depend on the DTMF technique with microcontroller type Atmega2560 [9]. Multiple sensors fire extinguisher robot can be remote control its operations in different modes based on DTMF, Bluetooth, global system for mobile (GSM), and Global positioning system (GPS) technologies. Temperature, flame, and smoke sensors have been used to detection of fire and the robot activity can be controlled by either DTMF or smartphone [10].

By using a mobile phone as a modem for controlling four home appliances has been designed and developed, the programmable interface controller (PIC) is used for the purpose of the control the switching of the output [11]. A home automation base on ZigBee and Arduino which is integrated through a home gateway with an android application output a system for remote control of indoor and outdoor appliances, a study of using these concepts in home automation, determining their activities and the feasibility of using them [12].

Today it is one of the most general remote control applications based on DTMF technology along with mobile network and GSM and after it was merged with the Arduino control board which forms a leap in the field of remote control applications in various fields [13]–[19]. Server independent systems used to control remote selected appliances depend on using the internet of things. The device can be controlled for this research started from industrial machine to consumer goods, the connectivity module using Arduino Uno microcontroller and ESP8266-01 [20]. The use of advanced microcomputers in smart control and remote monitoring applications to control and manage various systems using wireless and wired technologies, including, for example, electrical appliances, whether in homes, departments, or institutions, among others. The use of microcomputers of all kinds provides a suitable environment for carrying out remote control operations through ease of interfacing and compatibility with other devices used for this purpose [21].

In this work, remote control of electric appliances by using DTMF techniques interfacing with latch circuits is presented. This is via making a call by the owner mobile phone by sending commands in the form of analog tones through calling to auto-answer remote control panel phone (RCPP). Then the owner must click various keys to control various devices so that each key is used for on/off one device. This is done in such a way that using the first press of the key to turn ON the remote device and the second presses to switch it at OFF state. This process occurs using D-latch digital circuit.

2. PROPOSED DESIGN OUTLINE

The proposed wireless remote-control design is developed to control remote electric devices from any place regardless of time and space. The system is operated based on DTMF technology. In this technology, for the purpose of achieving control of electrical appliances wirelessly and remotely, cellular communication networks, two mobile phones, and other components are used for this purpose.

Figure 1 shows the block diagram of the proposed system. The system is divided into three parts denoted as, digital parts which are included buffer, 4-bits comparator integrated circuits (ICs), and latches ICs. The power parts which are consist of an upper limit of normal (ULN) 2003 driver, power supply unit, relays, and electric devices. Then, the third part is the tone generation, transmitting, receiving, and decoding (TGTRD) which are included tone decoder CM 8870 IC, RCPP, OM, and GSM network devices.

Figure 1. Proposed system block diagram

3. DTMF CONCEPTS

DTMF is a method used in mobile and landline phones for signal tone generation. The generated tones occur when any button is pressed on a keypad of the phone through making a call so that any pressing key will generate a separate signal tone matched with the pressed number. There are 12 standard signal tones. Ten represent the numbers from zero to nine, one asterisk (*) and one hashtag (#). The general mobile phone uses 12 keys [22], [23]. Figure 2, shows the standard phone keys with equivalent tone frequencies.

Each keypad number tone is formed by adding two frequencies, the low frequency (row line) and high frequency (column line) [24]. In other words, the output resultant tone is a convolution of low and high frequencies. Each of these tones can be expressed mathematically as (1):

$$f(t) = A_H \sin(2\pi f_H t) + A_L \sin(2\pi f_L t) \tag{1}$$

Where A_H, A_L are the amplitude of each frequency and f_H, f_L are the high and low frequencies [25]. DTMF tone frequencies have properties that can be summarized as:

- The difference between any two frequencies does not equal any of the other frequencies.
- No frequency is an integer multiple of another.
- The sum of any two frequencies does not equal any of the other sums of frequencies.

Table 1 shows all possibilities for generation tone signal frequencies of a keypad cell phone.

Keypad number	Low frequency (Hz)	High frequency (Hz)	Tone frequency (Hz)
1	697	1209	1906
2	697	1336	2033
3	697	1477	2174
4	770	1209	1979
5	770	1336	2106
6	770	1477	2247
7	852	1209	2061
8	852	1336	2188
9	852	1477	2329
*	941	1209	2150
0	941	1336	2277
#	941	1477	2418

Figure 2. Standard 12 keys of cell phone keypad with frequencies Hz

4. DETAILS PROPOSED SYSTEM COMPONENTS

4.1. Power parts

The power part consists of a power supply, driver, relays, and electric devices. The power supply unit as shown in Figure 3, is responsible for generating all required voltages in the design. Main input 220 VAC power given to step down transformer (220 to 12) VAC, then it is rectified using bridge rectifier (D1 D4) IN4007 and regulated by capacitor C1 470 μ F 25V. The output of the bridge rectifier is connected to two fixed regulators. First, the 12V regulator is denoted as 7812 to supply the relays and drivers. Second, the 5V regulator is denoted as 7805 to supply all system digital ICs. The resistance R1 330 Ω and red-LED D1 are used as an indicator. The ULN2003 driver IC is an array of Darlington transistors. This IC is used for interfacing with relays because of its high current and high voltage, it can carry a load of 500 ma, 50 v output.

Figure 3. Power supply unit circuit diagram

4.2. Digital parts

This part consists of buffer ICs type 74LS244, this circuit is used for the purpose of protecting the tone decoder from high load and for distribution of the binary tones to comparators. 4-bits comparator 74LS85, this device has two groups of entrances denoted as Group A and Group B. Group A connected to buffered binary tones, Group B connected to fixed values so that each pin can either be connected to VCC or GND matched with phone keypad key. Each comparator compares the two input groups and output logic high at pin (QA=B), these are used for ignition latch circuit that represents d-type flip-flop connected as D-latch circuit.

4.3. TGTRD parts

This part included OM, RCPP, and tone decoder. For OM, because it's used for tone generation, the keypad key sound must be activated at a maximum sound value. In the far place, RCPP is used as a receiver so the auto-answer service must be activated and the speaker volume level increases to the highest value. The CM8870 IC represents a tone decoder that performs the function of changing the received tone from the RCPP audio jack to 4-bit binary tones. This device requires a crystal oscillator, so the 3.597 MHz crystal oscillator is used.

5. DESCRIPTION OF THE FUNCTIONS OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

DTMF technique is used to identify which key is pressed in the keypad of OM during the call. The keypad represents a password entry device. Pressing any individual key in OM phone through the call will generate a unique tone matched with the pressed key which sends to RCPP. The RCPP receives the transmitted DTMF signals from OM, then connected to tone decoder IC CM8870 through headphone jack wires for the purpose of filtering, analyzing, and converting them from analog tone to 4-bits digital tone which is denoted by Q1, Q2, Q3, and Q4.

The 4-bits digital tones are connected to inputs of buffer IC type 74LS244. The output of this buffer is connected to twelve of 4-bits digital comparator IC (74LS85). Each comparator has two groups of 4-bits of inputs, denoted as group A and group B. group A inputs of all comparators connected to four outputs of the buffered circuit. While each bit of group B of individual comparator connected to VCC or GND matched with keypad key, so that for the first comparator group B must be connected to match with one key i.e., for group A tones equal to (Q4Q3Q2Q1=0001), therefore group B must be connected to GND VCC. And group B of the second comparator matched with pressing two keys, i.e., for group A tones equal to (Q1Q2Q3Q4=0010), therefore group B must be connected to VCC GND and so on for the other ten comparators. Table 2 summarized all probability of tone generating for all keypad keys and the equivalent status of group A and group B.

The digital comparator has three outputs denoted as (QA<B, QA=B, and QA>B). The output (QA=B) of each comparator is selected for connected to latch circuit in order to enable it for the first pressing key and disable it for the second pressing the same keypad key. The output of each latch circuit connected to an input of ULN2003 driver which leads to connect load relay that used to drive different kinds of electrical devices.

Table 2. All cases of tone generating

Keypad key	Binary tones group A	State of group B
1	0001	gnd gnd gnd vcc
2	0010	gnd gnd vcc gnd
3	0011	gnd gnd gnd vcc
4	0100	gnd gnd vcc gnd
5	0101	gnd gnd gnd vcc
6	0110	gnd gnd vcc gnd
7	0111	gnd gnd gnd vcc
8	1000	gnd gnd vcc gnd
9	1001	gnd gnd gnd vcc
*	1010	gnd gnd vcc gnd
0	1011	gnd gnd gnd vcc
#	1100	gnd gnd vcc gnd

6. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION AND SIMULATION

The proposed design consists of twelve stages, in addition to tone decoder and buffers. Each stage matches with one keypad key to control one electric device. Figure 4 explain in detail one stage circuit components but in this stage for the purpose of the simulation, the four-logic state device is used instead of CM8870 decoder and this stage may repeat 12 times to cover all system design by only changing the group A and group B. Figure 5 shows the first four stages circuit diagram of the real system circuit.

Figure 4. One stage circuit diagram

Figure 6. Switch ON electric device_4 for first pressed key 4

Figure 7. Switch OFF electric device_4 for second pressed key 4

Figure 8. Simulator single stage circuit diagram

Figure 9. First press key 1 for ON the electric device_1(Ele.dev.1=on)

Figure 10. Second press key 1 for OFF the electric device_1(Ele.dev.1=off)

In the same way, it is possible to simulate the operation and test of 12 electrical devices through the pressing of OM keypad keys to obtain the result shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Required actions of electric devices control

Key number	First pressed	Second pressed	Binary tones Q4Q3 Q2 Q1	Electric load device action
1	Ok		0001	Ele.dev.1=on
1		Ok	0001	Ele.dev.1=off
2	Ok		0010	Ele.dev.2=off
2		Ok	0010	Ele.dev.2=on
3	Ok		0011	Ele.dev.3=on
3		Ok	0011	Ele.dev.3=off
4	Ok		0100	Ele.dev.4=on
4		Ok	0100	Ele.dev.4=off
5	Ok		0101	Ele.dev.5=on
5		Ok	0101	Ele.dev.5=off
6	Ok		0110	Ele.dev.6=on
6		Ok	0110	Ele.dev.6=off
7	Ok		0111	Ele.dev.7=on
7		Ok	0111	Ele.dev.7=off
8	Ok		1000	Ele.dev.8=on
8		Ok	1000	Ele.dev.8=off
9	Ok		1001	Ele.dev.9=on
9		Ok	1001	Ele.dev.9=off
*	Ok		1010	Ele.dev.10=on
*		Ok	1010	Ele.dev.10=off
0	Ok		1011	Ele.dev.11=on
0		Ok	1011	Ele.dev.11=off
#	Ok		1100	Ele.dev.12=on
#		Ok	1100	Ele.dev.12=off

8. CONCLUSION

In recent years, the dependence on remote control over electrical appliances has increased, by depending on various technologies, such as GSM, DTMF, Wi-Fi, IoT, and others. The remote control is an excellent way to control electrical appliances such as water pumps, lamps, TV, cooling devices, heating appliances, and so on. The use of such technology is a solution and is very beneficial for people with

disabilities or the elderly or in large places such as departments, institutions, factories, and so on or for the purpose of reducing the expenses of electrical energy consumption, especially in the periods when the home or institution is free of people. In this research, a DTMF technology was chosen, due to the availability of GSM infrastructure and ease of use in addition to it is not limited in place and time. This research provided the ability to control 12 electrical devices remotely and wirelessly from anywhere in the world using the mobile phone and prevents unauthorized access to these appliances. An interesting and important feature of this design is the use of the same keypad number to switch ON and OFF the same remote electrical device. This feature is not present in other research, so it has become possible to control multiple numbers of devices using the standard mobile keypad, by relying on a D-type latching digital circuit that changes the state with every pressure the same key.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Preethi and R. Dharmalingam, "Based on the wireless bluetooth microcontroller controlling home appliances," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Electronics and Communication Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 440–444, 2017.
- [2] T. S. Gunawan, I. R. H. Yaldi, M. Kartiwi, and H. Mansor, "Performance Evaluation of Smart Home System using Internet of Things," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 400, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v8i1.pp400-411.
- [3] T. S. Gunawan *et al.*, "Prototype Design of Smart Home System using Internet of Things," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 107, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v7.i1.pp107-115.
- [4] P. A. Kumar, R. Reshav, B. Subhasish, and Kumar Nehai, "DTMF based home automation system," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 1355–1360, 2017.
- [5] S. K. Shareef and N. Shirisha, "Efficient automation using DTMF," *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3965–3966, 2020.
- [6] O. O. Kennedy, O. Modupe, P. O. Imhade, and O. Abayomi-Alli, "A model of automatic control for home appliances using DTMF technology," *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 266–272, 2017, doi: 10.36478/rjasci.2017.266.272.
- [7] N. Rohankar, M. Agrawal, R. Kodgule, K. Kolhe, and R. Verma, "DTMF based home and industrial automation," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Engineering and Technology*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 878–880, 2016.
- [8] B. Komal, T. Harsh, G. Maansi, and Kaushik Prachi, "Home automation using DTMF decoding," *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 184–187, 2019.
- [9] A. T. Noman, H. Rashid, M. A. M. Chowdhury, and M. S. Islam, "Design and implementation of a microcontroller based low cost DTMF controlled acoustic and visual detecting robot to monitor child and aged person," in *2019 International Conference on Electrical, Computer and Communication Engineering (ECCE)*, Feb. 2019, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/ECACE.2019.8679401.
- [10] H. Rashid, I. U. Ahmed, A. Ullah, M. F. Newaz, M. S. R. Robin, and S. M. T. Reza, "Multiple sensors based fire extinguisher robot based on DTMF, bluetooth and GSM technology with multiple mode of operation," in *2016 International Workshop on Computational Intelligence (IWCI)*, Dec. 2016, pp. 41–46, doi: 10.1109/IWCI.2016.7860336.
- [11] L. A. Akinyemi, O. O. Shoewu, N. T. Makanjuola, A. A. Ajasa, and C.O Folorunso, "Design and development of an automated home control system using mobile phone," *World Journal Control Science and Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 6–11, 2014.
- [12] S. F. Ibrahim, K. Mishra, and A. Munshi, "Comparison on approaches of home automation," *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education*, vol. 2, no. 5, pp. 95–99, 2016.
- [13] S. R. Zeebaree and H. M. Yasin, "Arduino based remote controlling for home: power saving, security and protection," *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, vol. 5, no. 8, pp. 266–272, 2014.
- [14] K. F. Al-Tabatabaie and Koraw Dara Hama, "Remote automation system control using arduino board," *International Journal of Latest Trends in Engineering and Technology*, vol. 8, no. 3, 2017, doi: 10.21172/1.83.022.
- [15] A. Min and A. Y. Y. Naing, "Arduino based home AC appliances control circuit using IR-signal," *Hinhada University Research Journal*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 8–16, 2015.
- [16] D. Anusha, P.M.Sarma, and M.N. SandhyaRani, "Appliance remote control using Arduino," *International Journal of Latest Trends in Engineering and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 35–41, 2013.
- [17] K. R. Babu, Mr.Ayınadis, Getahun, Engida, and Mr Missay.Mangesthu, "Implementation Arduino based house Automation using Bluetooth, Infrared," *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 7447–7455, 2019.
- [18] P. Sharma, P. Verma, K. Bhoomika, R. Kumar, and S. Baghel, "Home automation Using IR (Infrared) sensor and Arduino-Nano single Board Microcontroller," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 1305–1310, 2017.
- [19] N. David, C. Abafor, A. Ugochukwu, and O. Edoga, "Design of a home Automation System using Arduino," *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 795–803, 2015.
- [20] S. L. Mohan, B. S. Kumar, and M. Nihar, "Arduino based home automation using Internet of things (IoT)," *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 118, no. 17, pp. 769–778, 2018.
- [21] W. A. Salah and B. A. Zneid, "Evolution of microcontroller-based remote monitoring system applications," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 2354–2364, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v9i4.pp2354-2364.
- [22] K. Okeoghene Enalume, "Design and construction of a mobile phone based home and office appliances remote switching system," *American Journal of Embedded Systems and Applications*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 1, 2017, doi: 10.11648/j.ajesa.20170501.11.
- [23] G. Beza, H. Nasser, and A. H. A. "Remote controlling of an agricultural pump system based on the dual tone multi-frequency (DTMF) technique," *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, vol. 10, no. 10, pp. 1261–1274, 2015.
- [24] H. Raj, "DTMF based controlled robot vehicle," *International Journal for Scientific Research and Development*, vol. 2, no. 12, pp. 506–510, 2015.
- [25] G. Roshan, "DTMF based controller for efficiency improvement of a PV cell and relay operation control," *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications (IJERA)*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 2903–2911, 2012.
- [26] D. Cika and G. Darko, "Proteus virtual system modeling used for microcontroller education," 2010.